

The concept of disability and its social essence: modern approaches and theoretical analysis

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Abstract: This article scientifically analyzes the essence of the concept of disability, its historical evolution, interpretation based on the modern social model, and its social consequences in society. It also justifies the importance of studying disability in the context of human rights.

Keywords: disability, concept of disability, social model, medical model, functional limitation, social barriers, inclusion, discrimination, social integration, human rights, social equality, social adaptation, rehabilitation, stigma, social protection, social work, disability theories, society and disability.

Понятие инвалидности и её социальная сущность: современные подходы и теоретический анализ

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Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается понятие инвалидности, её содержание и сущность, а также эволюция подходов от традиционных к современным. Особое внимание уделяется переходу от медицинской модели к социальной модели инвалидности. Подчеркивается, что инвалидность является не только индивидуальной характеристикой, но и результатом социальных барьеров и ограничений окружающей среды. Анализируются социальные последствия инвалидности, такие как неравенство, дискриминация и ограниченный доступ к образованию и занятости. Также акцентируется внимание на важности рассмотрения инвалидности в контексте прав человека и социальной интеграции.

Ключевые слова: инвалидность, понятие инвалидности, социальная модель, медицинская модель, функциональные ограничения, социальные барьеры, инклюзия, дискриминация, социальная интеграция, права человека, социальное равенство, реабилитация, социальная работа

The Concept of Disability and Its Social Essence: Modern Approaches and Theoretical Analysis

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Annotation: This article examines the concept of disability, its content and essence, and its evolution from traditional to modern approaches. Special attention is given to the transition from the medical model to the social model of disability. The study highlights that disability is not only an individual condition but also a result of social barriers and environmental limitations. The paper analyzes the social consequences of disability, including inequality, discrimination, and limited access to education and employment. The importance of understanding disability within the framework of human rights and social inclusion is also emphasized.

Key words: disability, concept of disability, social model, medical model, functional limitation, social barriers, inclusion, discrimination, social integration, human rights, social equality, rehabilitation, social work.

Enter Today, the issue of disability is viewed not only as a medical problem, but also as a comprehensive social phenomenon. As society develops, the approach to disability is also changing radically. Previously, people with disabilities were considered a passive group in need of more help, but now they are recognized as equal members of society.

Disability is not a physical or mental defect in an individual, but a social condition that arises as a result of an imbalance between the individual and society.

The concept of disability and its content

Disability is understood as a partial or complete loss of a person's ability to work due to illness, injury or congenital defects. At the same time, in a modern approach, this concept is interpreted in a broader sense.

Disability:

- physical limitation;
- mental or psychological impairment;
- manifested by sensory (vision, hearing) impairments.

However, the important point is that the level of disability increases when these limitations are combined with barriers in society.

The evolution of the concept of disability

1. Traditional (charity) model

In this model, people with disabilities were seen as:

- in need of compassion;
- dependent on assistance;
- passive.

This approach limited their independence.

2. Medical model

In this approach:

- disability is viewed as a defect in the body;
- the main focus is on treatment and rehabilitation.

The disadvantage is that it ignores social factors.

3. Social model (modern approach)

- According to this model:
 - disability is the result of barriers in society;
 - the problem is not in the person, but in the environment.

- For example:
- • lack of ramps;
- • lack of inclusive education;
- • stereotypes.

The social nature of disability

The social nature of disability is manifested in:

- lack of equal opportunities in society;
- inadequate infrastructure;
- discrimination and stereotypes;
- limited access to information.

Thus, disability is not a biological problem, but a social one.

Key concepts: functional limitation and social barrier

- • **Functional limitation** — a physiological condition in an individual
- • **Social barrier** — a limitation created by society

Disability arises from the interaction of these two factors.

Social consequences of disability

In education

- • limited opportunities;
- • lack of special conditions.

In the field of work

- • discrimination;
- • job incompatibility.

Psychological state

- • social isolation;
- • low self-esteem.

Disability and human rights

The modern approach considers disability within the framework of human rights:

- the principle of equality;
- non-discrimination;
- the right to education and work;
- the right to freedom of movement.

A person with a disability is not a recipient of assistance, but a subject of law.

Disability from a social work perspective

- Social work interprets disability as:
 - a result of inequality;
 - a product of social injustice.
- Main tasks:
 - social protection;
 - rehabilitation;
 - adaptation;
 - creating a positive environment in society.

Conclusion and suggestions

Disability is not a flaw in an individual, but an indicator of how inclusive a society is. The more developed a society is, the less disability becomes a social barrier.

Offers:

It is necessary to formulate an approach to disability based on a fully social model. This will help to understand that the problem lies not in the individual, but in the obstacles in society.

In order to reduce stereotypes and stigmas related to disability in society, it is necessary to strengthen the activities of the media, educational institutions and social campaigns.

It is important to widely introduce inclusive education in the education system and create equal opportunities for all children.

It is necessary to expand the opportunities for free access to information for persons with disabilities (Braille, subtitles, audio formats).

It is recommended to adapt social infrastructure (roads, transport, buildings) based on universal design.

It is necessary to thoroughly teach modern approaches to disability in the training of social work specialists.

It is necessary to strengthen cooperation with public organizations to ensure the active participation of persons with disabilities in society.

It is advisable to expand the study of disability within the framework of human rights and develop scientific research in this direction.

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